

Treated Wastewater Reuse for Irrigation: Pros and Cons

1 **Abstract**

2 The appropriateness of using treated wastewater for crop or agricultural irrigation remains a bone
3 of contention among experts and policymakers. Here, we outline and analyze not only the benefits
4 but also the drawbacks of such a practice in order to suggest a way forward. To ensure that our
5 review reflects the state-of-the-art in terms of technological advances and best practices, only
6 literature published in the last decade is considered except for literature on the history of reuse.
7 The review begins by highlighting growing water scarcity, the history of wastewater reuse in
8 agriculture, and the limitations of existing studies. A short overview of the approach used in the
9 write-up is outlined after the introduction. It then proceeds with an in-depth look at three broad
10 areas: environmental impacts, public health impacts and economic impacts. In terms of
11 environmental impacts, effects on soil quality, water resources, plant growth, and soil microbial
12 communities are analyzed. For each sub-area, the positive effects are described before the
13 negative ones. The same approach is then applied to public health impacts, the focus of which is
14 on human exposure to heavy metals and pathogens, and economic impacts, which are assessed
15 with particular reference to investment cost and farm expenditure and income. Having weighed
16 the advantages and disadvantages in each area, innovative measures are proposed for
17 optimizing the benefits and mitigating the drawbacks of using treated wastewater for crop
18 irrigation.

19 **Keywords:** Salinization, Nutrients supply, Water scarcity, Water savings, Freshwater, Recovery

20 **1 Introduction**

21 Water, a valuable resource for all forms of life is continually becoming inaccessible, which is a
22 rapidly growing problem currently confronting our globe (Kummu et al., 2016). Some have
23 attributed this water scarcity to climate change, increased freshwater demand for municipal,
24 agricultural, and industrial uses. Ganjegunte et al. (2017) attribute the cause in the reduction of
25 freshwater availability in Texas (USA) to ongoing drought, and water stress caused by municipal
26 and industrial use of water. Agriculture which depends heavily on water and uses majority of the
27 abstracted freshwater globally, may be seriously affected negatively if an alternative source of
28 water for irrigation is not sought aside freshwater. The effect would be much greater in regions
29 of water scarcity such as the arid and semi-arid regions. According to Ventura et al. (2019)
30 about 70% of abstracted water is used for agricultural irrigation in arid and semi-arid regions of
31 the globe. Therefore, it's imperative that other alternative water sources such as desalinated
32 seawater and treated wastewater are sought for to complement the conventional freshwater
33 sources (surface water, groundwater). Utilization of treated wastewater effluent for irrigation as
34 an alternate water source has already been suggested (Ibekwe et al., 2018; Vergine et al.,
35 2017a).

36 The use of wastewater for irrigation dates to several decades of years back. In the early 20th
37 century, bigger cities in Europe were using wastewater for irrigation in what is known as
38 "sewage farms". It promoted agriculture but later became an environmental and health issue
39 (Gohil, 2000). Over the years, treated wastewater as an alternative water source for irrigation
40 has been a topic of discussion especially in regions of water scarcity. Treated wastewater for
41 irrigation is based on the simple concept of reuse as demonstrated in fig. 1. The reuse history of
42 treated wastewater globally, especially in China, demonstrates the possibility and practicality of
43 wastewater reuse in agriculture (Yi et al., 2011). Other countries such as Israel and Tunisia

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44 have also demonstrated sustainable use of recycled water in agriculture as an alternative to
45 complement the water demands (Bedbabis et al., 2014; Reznik et al., 2017). Several studies
46 have been conducted worldwide at both laboratory scale and field scale. These studies have
47 investigated the impacts of reuse practice on soil, plants/crops, water and public health as well
48 as the economic feasibility. Studies on soil include impacts on soil pH, salinity, nutrients
49 accumulation, heavy metals accumulation, electrical conductivity, changes in soil structure and
50 texture, sodium adsorption ratio and changes in soil microbial community (Bedbabis et al., 2014;
51 Ibekwe et al., 2018; Klay et al., 2010; Singh et al., 2012).

52 Nutrients absorption, heavy metals accumulation and heavy metals translocation to fruits or plant
53 edible parts characterize studies on plants (Kalavrouziotis et al., 2012). Public health-
54 related studies have focused on possible contamination of edible parts of plants by pathogens
55 as well as possible human exposure to pathogens and heavy metals (Akponikpè et al., 2011;
56 Farhadkhani et al., 2018). The works of Ruiz-Rosa et al. (2016) and Reznik et al. (2017)
57 explored the economic feasibility or implication of treated wastewater reuse in agricultural
58 irrigation to other water sources such as surface water, groundwater and desalinated
59 seawater/brackish water. The findings of the various studies have shed more light on
60 wastewater reuse in agriculture including the benefits and drawbacks. However, the
61 appropriateness of using treated wastewater for crop irrigation remains a bone of contention
62 among experts and policymakers. In addition, the findings of these studies are also highly
63 segregated and most often skewed towards either pros or cons, falling short of a detailed analysis
64 of both in one study. Limited studies exist where the different pros and cons are
65 extensively analyzed and discussed in a single research paper.

66 Therefore, this paper reviews the different benefits and drawbacks of using treated wastewater
67 for agricultural irrigation by outlining, analyzing and discussing the various cases with focus on

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68 environmental impacts, economic impacts and public health impacts in a single paper; it
69 proposes interventions to help optimise the benefits and mitigate the drawbacks of such a reuse
70 practice. It provides insight for researchers and policymakers in making informed decisions on
71 matters of treated wastewater reuse for irrigation.

72 *Figure 1: Treated wastewater reuse concept*

73 **2 Review Approach**

74 The study utilized the systematic review process, using the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
75 Literature which is older than ten (10) years of publication is excluded from the review except for
76 literature on the history of reuse. This was to ensure that relatively most current knowledge on
77 treated wastewater reuse for irrigation is used for the review process to highlight current
78 situations and to avoid using information which are currently invalid due to the advancement of
79 technology and knowledge. Direct reuse of treated industrial wastewater effluent was excluded
80 from the study. An exception to this exclusion criterion is treated effluent from brewery and
81 agronomic industry due to relative similarities in the effluent characteristics with municipal
82 wastewater. The review begins with an introduction highlighting growing water scarcity, the
83 history of reuse, and limitations in existing studies. It then proceeded with an in-depth look at
84 three broad themes: environmental impacts, public health impacts, and economic impacts after
85 the review approach. In terms of environmental impacts, effects on soil quality, water resources,
86 plant growth, and soil microbial communities were analyzed. For each sub-theme, the pros are
87 discussed before the cons. In each case, the benefits or drawbacks are highlighted, analyzed and
88 their implications discussed. The same approach is then applied to the other two themes. In
89 the case of public health impacts, we focused on human exposure to heavy metals and
90 pathogens. Economic impacts are assessed with regards to extra investment cost and farm
91 expenditure and income. In the characterization process, impacts that promote agricultural yield,

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92 water savings and contribute to environmental protection were considered beneficial and the
93 opposite considered as detrimental. When an impact has both positive and negative effects, the
94 most profound effect was used. However, in the case of nutrients provision by treated wastewater,
95 the characterization was based on both effects. The profound effects of supporting plant growth
96 and improving plant yield (fertilization effect) represented the positive aspects while possible plant
97 toxicity and groundwater pollution (excess nutrients) were considered as adverse effects. In this
98 review, trace organic compounds, microplastics, and antibiotic resistant genes and bacteria were
99 given special consideration in relation to treated wastewater irrigation. Currently, these
100 substances have become topic of discussion among experts and policymakers because of the
101 environmental and health impacts associated with them. Having weighed the various benefits and
102 drawbacks in each theme, innovative measures are suggested for maximizing the benefits and
103 mitigating the drawbacks. The use of the words “plants” and “crops” are used interchangeably in
104 this paper.

105 *Figure 2: Schematic illustrations of themes for the review and structure: (a) Environmental impacts associated*
106 *with treated wastewater irrigation; (b) Public health risk arising from the use of treated wastewater for crop*
107 *irrigation; (c) Economic impacts of treated wastewater irrigation*

108 Using the schematic illustration (fig. 2), the positive and negative impacts of treated wastewater
109 irrigation are outlined, analyzed and discussed. From this section onward the use of the word
110 “wastewater” will have the same meaning as “treated wastewater” unless otherwise specified.

111 **3 Environmental Impacts of Treated Wastewater Reuse for Irrigation**

112 Reusing of treated wastewater for irrigation presents numerous environmental benefits and
113 challenges. The extent of impacts is dependent on the quality of the treated effluent and other
114 external factors. Wastewater effluent quality is characterized by the physicochemical and
115 microbial compositions. According to Elgallal et al. (2016), the scale of an impact will be
116 determined by the effluent’s chemical composition and concentration, and the solubility and

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117 toxicity of the substances present in the wastewater effluent. Other factors include the rate and
118 frequency of irrigation, soil properties and climatic conditions.

119 **3.1 Soil Impacts**

120 **3.1.1 Nutrients Supply**

121 Wastewater irrigation adds important macro- and micronutrients to the soil. Wastewater is a
122 valuable source of nitrogen (N), potassium (K), phosphorus (P), zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), manganese
123 (Mn) and copper (Cu) due to its composition (Qadir and Scott, 2010). Several studies have
124 reported an increase in soil macro- and micronutrients after wastewater irrigation. Ganjegunte et
125 al. (2017) observed an improvement in the soil nutrient content after a six-year irrigation period.
126 They reported an increase in both nitrates and potassium; pre-study nitrate concentration of the
127 soil solution¹ ranged from 269 to 321 mg/L and increased to a range of 910 to 2271 mg/L after
128 the study. An increase from 59 mg/L to 195 mg/L was also observed for potassium. In other
129 studies, soil fertility levels were significantly improved concerning nitrogen, phosphorus,
130 potassium and micronutrients after soils were irrigated with treated wastewater (Galavi et al.,
131 2010; Singh et al., 2012). Again, an increase in phosphorus content was reported by Bedbabis et
132 al. (2014), which they suggested was as a result of the fertilization effect of the treated wastewater
133 used for the irrigation. Treated wastewater irrigation is hence key to maintaining and improving
134 the quality of arable soils, an essential medium for food production.

135 Over 90% of the world's food is produced on soil (directly or indirectly), and a reduction in any of
136 the soil's nutrients can negatively affect plant yield (FAO, 2015). Plant growth greatly depends on
137 soil nutrients, and deficiency in nutrients can limit growth and productivity (Morgan & Connolly,
138 2013). The importance of nutrients supply by wastewater is demonstrated by outlining the roles

¹¹ Soil solution refers to the soil's film moisture containing dissolved substances (Merriam-Webster Dictionary¹).

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139 these nutrients play in the physiological and morphological development of plants and as well as
140 other plant processes.

141 **Nitrogen:** Is a major nutrient required by plants for physiological and biochemical processes. It
142 facilitates the growth and development of plant's stem, leaves and other vegetative parts.
143 Phosphorus and potassium uptake in plants and subsequent utilization are influenced by nitrogen
144 (Bloom, 2015; Hemerly, 2016; Leghari et al., 2016). It is so essential that one third of the world's
145 food could be lost if additional supply to augment plant growth is neglected. Nitrogen supply is
146 critical for the formation of important biological molecules, DNA and RNA which are carriers of
147 genetic information (Aczel, 2019). Enzymatic reactions in plants are catalyzed by nitrogen. It plays
148 an important role in photosynthesis, a food-producing process in plants that make use of
149 chlorophyll. This green pigment (chlorophyll) used by plants in absorbing light is made up of a
150 significant portion of nitrogen and therefore its reduction affects photosynthesis. Nitrogen
151 improves the quality and quantity of certain crops such as leafy vegetables and grains. Inadequate
152 supply to plants can leads to stunted growth, chlorosis, low protein content in seeds, and reduction
153 in crop yield caused by early maturity (Khalid, 2018).

154 **Phosphorus:** Another essential macronutrient attainable through wastewater irrigation. It is an
155 indispensable nutrient needed for the growth and productivity of plants. Phosphorus plays an
156 important role in many processes in plants including germination of seeds, metabolism of
157 carbohydrates, division of cells, and roots and stalk development (Malhotra et al., 2018; Razaq et
158 al., 2017). Phosphorus constitutes many of plant's proteins, nucleic acid, coenzymes, and aids in
159 energy transfer (Jones & Olson-Rutz, 2016). Plant uses phosphorus for the formation of
160 biomolecules, formation of high energy molecules for photosynthesis and membrane structure
161 maintenance. The capacity of leguminous plants in the fixation of nitrogen is also enhanced by

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162 the availability of phosphorus. Its deficiency decreases photosynthesis and impacts plant growth
163 negatively (Malhotra et al., 2018; Razaq et al., 2017).

164 **Potassium:** Supports plant growth and development in several ways. Plant's ability to resist
165 diseases and overcome drought stress is influenced by potassium (Crouse, 2018). Potassium is
166 involved in the activation of enzymes, regulation of the closing and opening of stomata and acts
167 as osmoticum for cellular growth. Being the most abundant cation within plant cells, it helps in
168 cellular anion balancing. In agriculture, having sufficient potassium is crucial since its deficiency
169 leads to chlorosis of leaves, browning of leaves, and impeded growth (Morgan & Connolly, 2013).

170 **Micronutrients:** These nutrients are needed in relatively small quantities and serve several
171 functions in plants such as being enzyme activators and respiration catalysts. They are involved
172 in chlorophyll synthesis, nitrogen fixation, control of oxidation-reduction systems, and regulating
173 metabolic activities (Jones & Olson-Rutz, 2016).

174 Fourteen out of the seventeen essential nutrients needed for plant growth, development, and
175 productivity can be derived from soil (Parikh & James, 2012). Therefore, the addition of nutrients
176 to the soil through wastewater irrigation contributes greatly towards agriculture sustainability by
177 making available essential nutrients for plant absorption.

178 **3.1.2 Organic Carbon/Matter**

179 Treated wastewater may be rich in organic carbon/matter than conventional surface water and
180 groundwater. Therefore, the reuse of wastewater could be a viable and valuable source of organic
181 carbon for soils to promote plant growth. Galavi et al. (2010) reported an increase in organic
182 carbon/matter percentage in wastewater irrigated soil compared to the control soil. Similar
183 observations have been made in other studies (Adrover et al., 2012; Becerra-Castro et al., 2015;
184 Farhadkhani et al., 2018).

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185 Soil characteristics such as nutrients turnover, soil stability, colour, and nutrient holding capacity
186 which are essential are influenced by organic carbon content. Serving as a food source for
187 microbes, organic carbon can help improve soil stability by providing energy to microorganisms
188 to bind soil particles into aggregates (Pluske et al., 2020). Soil aggregation and stability coupled
189 with porosity are imperative for good aeration of soil and water infiltration (FAO, 2017). Such
190 improvements do not only ensure an adequate supply of air for microbial activities and adequate
191 water to the roots of plants but may also prevent farm flooding in the case of a heavy rainfall
192 event. A review by Murphy (2015) indicated that increasing organic matter in the soil leads to
193 improvements in soil compactibility, soil erodibility, soil buffering capacity against acidification,
194 nutrient recycling, and nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphur) availability.

195 **3.1.3 Increased Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR)**

196 Sodium absorption ratio (SAR) reflects the suitability of irrigation water on soil. It may computed
197 from the calcium, sodium and magnesium ions concentrations in soil or irrigation water (Oster et
198 al., 2016). It is highly correlated with exchangeable sodium percentage and therefore it is
199 considered as a measure of a soil's sodacity. Basically, SAR indicates the effect of only sodium
200 ions on soil structure (Marchuk & Rengasamy, 2010). Wastewater irrigated soils turn to have
201 elevated SAR than freshwater irrigated soils. In one study, an increase of 113.6% was observed
202 in soil irrigated with treated wastewater relative to soil irrigated with conventional water (Zema et
203 al., 2012). Many wastewater irrigation research has reported higher soil SAR after irrigation; with
204 some attributing the elevation to the relatively high sodium content or SAR of the irrigation water
205 (Bedbabis et al., 2014; Ganjegunte et al., 2017; SouDakouré et al., 2013). Factors such as
206 composition of wastewater, type and frequency of irrigation, soil type, and agricultural
207 management practices may influence the SAR of wastewater irrigated soils. High SAR of irrigation
208 water could have adverse impacts on crops and soil.

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209 In a related study, Aamer Maqsood et al. (2015) found that high SAR coupled with a high rate of
210 boron application decreased maize growth and caused plant toxicity. The ionic balance within the
211 plant tissues was also reduced. Elevated SAR levels can cause calcium deficiency in plants by
212 increasing sodium in the root medium and limiting calcium availability (Imran et al., 2010).
213 Irrigating crops with wastewater could increase the sodium content of the soil and significantly
214 reduce dissolve organic carbon sorption (Mavi et al., 2012). Such reduction may adversely affect
215 soil fertility and impedes agriculture productivity. One soil property at risk of damage by high SAR
216 is structural stability. Loss of soil structural stability caused by clay deflocculation and movement
217 at elevated SAR have been reported in literature. The permeability of a soil or hydraulic
218 conductivity decreases with increasing SAR (Arienzo et al., 2012; Oster et al., 2016). This affects
219 the soil's ability to conduct water to the root zone which can lead to plant death especially for
220 deep rooted plants. The soil moisture content could also be negatively affected since water cannot
221 infiltrate through the profile. As already mentioned, other factors such as soil type may also play
222 a role in this effect aside the sodicity effect of the wastewater.

223 **3.1.4 Soil Salinization**

224 Salinization of soil refers to the accumulation of water-soluble species or salts in a soil. The
225 soluble species could be cation (sodium, magnesium, iron, calcium) or anion (chloride) (Rojas et
226 al., 2016). It is considered as the most relevant parameter in the suitability determination of
227 irrigation water. Electrical conductivity (EC) of soil is a measure of the soil's salinity and can also
228 be expressed as total dissolved solids (TDS) (Shakir et al., 2017). Wastewater irrigation could
229 lead to temporal and long-term salinization due to its salts (cations and anions) content. A tomato
230 cultivated farm irrigated with treated wastewater experienced temporal salinization during the
231 summer period but return to normalcy at the end of the winter period (Vergine et al., 2017a). The
232 authors attributed the temporal increase to high irrigation regime and lack of rainfall which resulted
233 in the accumulation of salts from the wastewater. The measured EC values of wastewater

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234 irrigated plots in another study were higher than the EC before the irrigation exercise. The
235 suggested cause was the relatively high salinity of the wastewater (Farhadkhani et al., 2018).
236 Many authors have reported elevated salinity in soils after irrigation with treated wastewater
237 (Kallel et al., 2012; Klay et al., 2010; Shakir et al., 2017).

238 High soil salinity reduces agricultural productivity by causing deficit in plant water uptake and
239 altering the physiology and anatomy of plants. It is considered a major threat to food security
240 (Karan & Subudhi, 2012). At high salinity, osmotic stress occurs in the root zone of plants thereby
241 limiting plant water potential. As additional ions continue to penetrate the plant cells, ionic stress
242 also sets in. These stresses could lead to growth reduction and toxicity (Djanaguiraman & Prasad,
243 2013). In a salinity test involving basil plants, physiological water scarcity caused by high osmotic
244 stress was suggested as the cause for the significant reduction in the growth of the plant (Heidari,
245 2012). Bybordi et al. (2010) also observed a gradual decrease in the height of five canola cultivars
246 as the salinity level increased. Chloride ion induced salinity will cause growth inhibition in non-salt
247 tolerant plants (Djanaguiraman & Prasad, 2013). The magnitude of the impact of soil salinity is
248 plant-dependent. In a non-salt adapted plant, the adverse effect can be detrimental, but the effect
249 would be less in a salt-tolerant plant. It is therefore important, to control the salinity of treated
250 wastewater used for irrigation to avoid salinization of the soil.

251 **3.1.5 Soil Structure and Hydraulic Properties**

252 Irrigation water influences the structure and properties of soil, especially for long-term irrigation
253 regimes. The influence could be beneficial or adverse depending on the composition of the water.
254 Using treated wastewater for irrigation turns to have a more negative effect on soil than tap-water,
255 surface and groundwater due to the relatively high salts (cations and anions) composition and
256 other constituents. In Israel, a long-term wastewater irrigation exercise adversely affected the

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257 hydraulic properties of the irrigated soil and changed the water flow regime (Assouline & Narkis,
258 2011). The hydraulic conductivity, sorptivity and cumulative infiltration were reduced.

259 Degradation of soil structure arising from the use of treated wastewater has been reported by
260 various authors (Bardhan et al., 2016; Levy et al., 2014; SouDakouré et al., 2013). The work of
261 SouDakouré et al. (2013) reported a drastic reduction in the structural porosity of a wastewater
262 irrigated soil compared to a non-wastewater irrigated soil. The pore volume reduced sharply with
263 an increase in bulk density. Hydraulic conductivity determination by the Beerkan method failed as
264 a result of a low infiltration rate, an indication of the severity of the impact. The measured
265 infiltration rate was 2.5 times lower than the corresponding tap-water irrigated soil. Reuse of the
266 wastewater for the irrigation had led to the accumulation of sodium, bicarbonates, and increased
267 pH. This caused a collapse of the structural pore network and induced organic matter dissolution
268 leading to the covering of the soil surface. Levy et al. (2014) asserted that wastewater irrigation
269 could cause exchangeable sodium accumulation in the soil subsurface layers. They argued that
270 such accumulation can degrade the soil structure through swelling of clay minerals. The resulted
271 degradation may adversely affect water flow in the soil layers and possibly prevent aeration
272 temporally.

273 Adverse impacts on soil-water relationship arising from reuse could significantly affect crop
274 production negatively. Plant growth depends greatly on soil-water relationship since both are the
275 fundamental media supporting the plant. Reductions in hydraulic conductivity, water holding
276 capacity and infiltration rate as discussed earlier will affect water availability to plants. The soil's
277 inability to hold water can limit water availability to shallow-rooted plants while its inability to
278 conduct or transport water can affect deep-rooted crops badly in-terms of water accessibility. The
279 impacts could be different for each zone of the soil profile considering other factors such as plant
280 uptake characteristics (Assouline & Narkis, 2011).

281 **3.2 Water Resources**

282 One of the most important reasons for practicing wastewater irrigation is the possibility of using
283 the effluent as a water source. Therefore, treated effluent could be regarded as an alternate water
284 source for supporting plant growth.

285 **3.2.1 Reduction in Water Abstraction**

286 Water abstraction refers to the drawing of water from surface water sources, groundwater, or a
287 storage reservoir (Hoekstra, 2015). It has been estimated that about 80% of the extracted water
288 is discharged as wastewater and 70% of the discharged amount can be recovered (Yi et al.,
289 2011). One of the main purposes of water abstraction is for agricultural irrigation. Considering the
290 growing water scarcity and high demand for crop production, reuse of marginal quality water
291 (treated wastewater) for irrigation presents a great opportunity in reducing the quantity of water
292 extracted for irrigation, and minimizing water stress on freshwater sources, especially in regions
293 of water scarcity. Reuse of treated wastewater for irrigation saved the city of Ait Melloul (Morocco)
294 4 Mm³ of water annually that would have been extracted from freshwater sources for the irrigation
295 of a 400-hectare forest (Benzine, 2012). Also, a field study in Saudi Arabia, saved 60% of
296 groundwater when treated wastewater was used for irrigation (Balkhair et al., 2013).

297 China, Israel, Australia and many other arid and semi-arid countries use a substantial quantity of
298 reclaimed water for irrigation. Agricultural irrigation accounts for the majority of over 80% reuse
299 of wastewater effluent in Israel (Angelakis & Snyder, 2015). During a period of drought in
300 Australia, treated wastewater became the primary source of water for irrigation for most of the
301 farmers in the Werribee irrigation district. The city of Melbourne (Australia) is actively engaged in
302 wastewater irrigation, having two large peri-urban irrigation schemes (Barker et al., 2011). Such
303 schemes augment the existing surface water and groundwater resources.

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304 The possibility of treated wastewater irrigation is very significant in addressing the agricultural
305 water demand and relieving freshwater resources of stress (Jaramillo & Restrepo, 2017). In many
306 water-scarce regions, wastewater has supported agricultural irrigation (Corcoran et al., 2010) for
307 many years by being an alternate and primary agricultural water source, due to limited freshwater
308 sources in these regions. To a large extent, it has solved or minimized the agricultural water
309 demand problems of these areas and contribute to addressing the global water deficit (Zhang &
310 Shen, 2019). With agriculture irrigation consuming 70% of the world's water resources (Pedrero
311 et al., 2010), using treated wastewater to irrigate crops could ensure both agriculture and water
312 sustainability through the provision of water to crops and limiting the demand on freshwater
313 sources.

314 **3.2.2 Protect and Promote Water Quality**

315 The application of treated wastewater for irrigation could preserve and promote the quality of
316 freshwater resources in two major ways: (i) reduction of water pollution through the avoidance of
317 discharge of effluent into water bodies (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015) and (ii) avoidance of water
318 pollution by fertilizers through the reduction of mineral fertilizer application in agriculture
319 (Ungureanu et al., 2018). Reusing treated effluent for irrigation diverts both organic and inorganic
320 substances to agriculture use which could have increased the pollution load of the receiving water
321 if it was discharged.

322 Globally, about 5500 billion m³ of water is polluted annually by wastewater discharges (Zhang &
323 Shen, 2019). Wastewater discharges elevate the level of nitrates, phosphates, micronutrients,
324 and in some cases heavy metals in receiving waters. Such elevation could adversely affect the
325 water ecosystem as well as agriculture activities downstream that rely on these water sources. A
326 common problem associated with such discharges on water sources is eutrophication, which
327 when not controlled results in depletion of oxygen, death of aquatic fishes (Ji, 2017), and in

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328 extreme cases a lifeless water ecosystem. Therefore, any practice that seeks to reuse treated
329 wastewater provides an innovative approach in maintaining the quality of receiving waters and
330 prevents pollution.

331 Mineral fertilizers used in improving soil quality and plant growth have the potential of polluting
332 freshwater through leaching and surface runoff (Khan et al., 2018). However, wastewater
333 irrigation reduces the risk of such pollution. The fertilization effect of wastewater limits the quantity
334 of mineral fertilizer application thereby protecting groundwater and surface water from possible
335 nutrients leaching and runoff caused by excessive mineral fertilizer application. In coastal and
336 saline areas, salinization of groundwater arising from saline water or seawater intrusion caused
337 by over-extraction of groundwater (Alfarrah & Walraevens, 2018) can be minimized when
338 wastewater irrigation is practiced. It can therefore be concluded that, wastewater irrigation could
339 acts as a barrier against water pollution arising from mineral fertilizers and effluent discharges.

340 **3.2.3 Water Pollution**

341 Wastewater irrigation could protect freshwater sources as already discussed in section 3.2.3,
342 however, it also has the potential of polluting both surface water and groundwater. The quality of
343 treated wastewater is dependent on a number of factors. The original source of the water, type of
344 usage and the treatment technology all influence the final quality of the wastewater. Hence treated
345 wastewater may still contain some pollutants or contaminants (Schacht et al., 2016).
346 Contaminants in wastewater can be of chemical, inert/physical or microbiological nature.
347 Chemical pollutants include inorganic compounds (nutrients), heavy metals, nanoparticles, and
348 organic pollutants (e.g. pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, endocrine disruption
349 compounds, disinfection by-products) (Fatta-Kassinos et al., 2011). Non-degradable and non-
350 reactive substances such as suspended solids, grit, sand, and floating solids like wood and
351 plastics (Akpor et al., 2014) constitute the inert contaminants. Microbiological contaminants

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352 include bacteria (e.g. *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp.), helminths (e.g. *Ancylostoma*), protozoans,
353 schistosomes, and viruses (e.g. *Hepatitis A*, *Norovirus*, *Rotavirus*) (Jaramillo & Restrepo, 2017).
354 Kitajima et al. (2020) state that severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, SARS-CoV-2,
355 causing the ongoing global pandemic COVID-19, can be also present in wastewater.
356 Concentration levels of contaminants varies with region and the level of wastewater treatment
357 (Jaramillo & Restrepo, 2017).

358 These contaminants can pollute water bodies through wastewater irrigation notably the ones
359 which are not or partially degraded during wastewater treatment. This could adversely affects the
360 water ecosystem particularly for aquatic fishes, due to the endocrine disruption effect of some of
361 these contaminants (Schacht et al., 2016). Intensive application of wastewater in addition to other
362 factors could cause leaching of nutrients such as nitrates into groundwater (Gerstl & Graber,
363 2011; Zufiaurre et al., 2020) leading to elevated nitrogen concentration levels. This results in the
364 deterioration of groundwater quality and increases the cost of treatment in the case of domestic
365 usage.

366 Suspended solids in wastewater could clog pores of wastewater irrigated soils, reduce their
367 infiltration rate and increase runoff. During irrigation solids get deposited in the soil pores and with
368 time reduces both the microspores and mesopores of the soil. This reduces the soil porosity and
369 infiltration rate and increases the chances of higher runoff (Albalasmeh et al., 2020; Bardhan et
370 al., 2016). Through irrigation runoff, nutrients (N, P), effluent-derived organic xenobiotics and
371 other contaminants can enter the aquatic ecosystems (Gerstl & Graber, 2011). The entering of
372 effluent-derived organic pollutants into surface waters could potentially affects endocrine system
373 of aquatic organisms and subsequently change the dynamics of the water ecosystem. Runoff of
374 nutrients on the other hand may lead to eutrophication, a common phenomenon associated with
375 polluted surface waters. Eutrophication restrict the use of water by further degrading the quality

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376 of water (Lawniczak et al., 2016). It also poses threat to fishes through oxygen depletion. Fishes
377 depend on oxygen for survival, but the phenomenon of eutrophication promotes algae growth
378 which deprive the fishes of this important gas. Another notable water pollution that could result
379 from treated wastewater irrigation is groundwater salinization. Salinization may occur when the
380 treated effluent is high in salinity. Wastewater irrigation could increase the salinity of soil and leach
381 salts beyond the root zones (Segal et al., 2011). The salts can be transported further downwards
382 into groundwater, especially for aquifers closer to the earth surface. Such salts intrusion
383 negatively affect the groundwater quality and limit its usage for both domestic and agricultural
384 purposes (Mirzavand et al., 2020; Vengosh, 2014). Therefore, wastewater irrigation should be
385 carried out with care to avoid possible contamination of surface water and groundwater resources
386 by incorporating pollution prevention measures.

387 **3.3 Plant Growth Impacts**

388 The nutrients content of treated wastewater makes it attractive for irrigation. It supports plant
389 growth through the provision of nutrients and fulfill the agricultural water requirements for crop
390 production (Lu et al., 2015). Generally, the supply of nutrients is beneficial for plant growth but
391 also in cases of excess supply, plant toxicity may occur.

392 **3.3.1 Improved Nutrients Availability and Uptake**

393 Wastewater irrigation has positive impacts on plant growth (Vergine et al., 2017a). In many
394 instances, the use had significantly improved yield and accelerated the growth of plants (Aziz and
395 Farissii, 2014) due to easy nutrients availability and uptake. An increase of 25.6%, 86.7% and
396 63% in plant's height, leaf area index, and biomass yield respectively have been observed
397 compared to their conventional water counterpart (Zema et al., 2012). In a two-cycle cultivation
398 of lettuce, a significant difference in weight was noticed between wastewater irrigated lettuce and
399 potable water irrigated lettuce. The former was 48% and 100% larger than the latter during the

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400 first and second cycles respectively. It has been asserted that wastewater could supply nutrients
401 during an entire growing season (Urbano et al., 2017). The supply of ammonia by wastewater
402 increased the yield of artichoke by 20% in a related study (Gatta et al., 2016). Singh et al. (2012)
403 observed an increase in seed weight and yield of rabi crops irrigated with wastewater than rabi
404 crops irrigated with well water and attributed the observed increase to the fertilization effect of the
405 wastewater.

406 The application of treated wastewater makes both macro- and micronutrients available for uptake
407 by plants. Plant nutrient uptake is influenced by root system and concentration of nutrients at the
408 root surface. Most nutrients are taken up in their ionic or charged form and not elemental or
409 uncharged form (Jones & Olson-Rutz, 2016). Treated wastewater contains nitrogen in the form
410 of nitrates and ammonium which makes nitrogen readily available for plant uptake. Phosphorus
411 is present mainly as orthophosphate and potassium as potassium ion (Aziz & Farissi, 2014) which
412 are easily accessible to plants. Therefore, treated wastewater promotes growth and yield by
413 providing nutrients in their appropriate form for easy uptake by plants. For instance in a study, the
414 use of wastewater to irrigate lettuce increased the yield up to 50% by supplying nitrogen in the
415 form of nitrates (Vergine et al., 2017b).

416 **3.3.2. Plant Toxicity**

417 Refers to the decrease in plant growth and quality due to excess nutrients (Mccauley et al., 2011).
418 In wastewater irrigation, plant toxicity arises from the supply macronutrients, organic compounds
419 and trace elements. Wastewater irrigation has shown to increase the trace elements of both soil
420 and plants (Galavi et al., 2010; Kalavrouziotis et al., 2012). Such accumulation could induce
421 toxicity when the concentrations are above the threshold. The magnitude of increase is dependent
422 on plant uptake capacity, soil properties (Hussain et al., 2019), and treated wastewater

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423 composition. Copper, cadmium, lead, nickel, zinc, chromium and iron are the commonly
424 accumulated elements (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015).

425 Even though copper, nickel, zinc and iron promote plant growth yet, their supply and uptake in
426 excess amount are detrimental to plants (Batarseh et al., 2011; Parveen et al., 2015). Their
427 accumulation could adversely impact the biochemical processes of plants and affect growth
428 negatively. Such contamination alters the soil's chemistry and affects growth (Parveen et al.,
429 2015). For example, excess uptake of zinc causes poor germination, leaf chlorosis, and wilting of
430 older leaves (Crouse, 2018). Aside from the reported trace element toxicity, macronutrients
431 toxicity could also occur. This happens when fertilizer application is done without factoring the
432 fertilization effect of treated wastewater. Excess (i) nitrogen causes delayed maturity and weak
433 stems (ii) phosphorus will inhibits zinc uptake leading to zinc deficiency and (iii) potassium will
434 induce magnesium deficiency by reducing magnesium uptake (Mccauley et al., 2011). This
435 drawback is quite dicey since the causes of toxicity are the very nutrients (except heavy metals)
436 that promote plant growth when not in excess.

437 Plant toxicity could also arise from the uptake and accumulation of organic xenobiotic compounds
438 such as endocrine disrupting compounds, pharmaceuticals, personal care products, etc. Treated
439 wastewater usually contains these compounds, and wastewater irrigation is one of the important
440 routes by which the xenobiotics are introduced into the soil for plants uptake (Becerra et. al., 2015;
441 Kassinos et al., 2011). Kassinos et. al. (2011) reviewed the works of other authors and presented
442 study cases where xenobiotics were taken up by plants because of their availability through
443 irrigation. In one of the studies, oxytetracycline induced toxicity in alfalfa (*Medicago sativa L.*) by
444 inhibiting the growth of the shoot and root by up to 61% and 85% respectively. Another study from
445 the review also established the phytotoxicity of enrofloxacin on *Cucumis sativus*, *Lactuca sativa*,

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446 *Phaseolus vulgaris* and *Raphanus sativus*. Therefore, treated wastewater irrigation could induce
447 toxicity in plants through bioaccessibility of organic xenobiotic compounds.

448 **3.4 Microbial Impacts**

449 Soil microbial communities are essential part of the soil ecosystem. A complex system of
450 interrelation between the physicochemical properties and biological components of soil forms the
451 basis of the communities (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). The use of treated wastewater for
452 irrigation may cause disturbances within these communities and impacts soil fertility and
453 productivity. These microbiological alterations in the soil involve a variety of complex variables
454 such as climate, soil, and wastewater characteristics (Lopes et al., 2015).

455 **3.4.1 Microbial Activities**

456 Microorganisms in soil respond to wastewater irrigation in several ways, including increase in
457 microbial activities and biomass (Adrover et al., 2012; Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). Very few
458 studies have reported the opposite as was in the case of Kayikcioglu (2012). The activities of soil
459 microorganisms increasing due to wastewater irrigation have been reported in both short-term
460 and long-term irrigation regimes. During a four-year irrigation study, it was observed that the
461 hydrolysis activity of wastewater irrigated soil was higher than the corresponding freshwater
462 irrigated soil. The increase negatively correlated with the dissolved organic carbon (DOC) of the
463 soil, implying DOC degradation by the microbes (Elifantz et al., 2011). According to del Mar
464 Alguacil et al. (2012), the activities of dehydrogenase, urease, protease, β -glucosidase, and
465 alkaline phosphatase enzymes were significantly higher in soils irrigated with treated wastewater
466 than freshwater irrigated soils. The quality of the wastewater in terms of nutrients and organic
467 matter may have stimulated different metabolic pathways or microbial activities within the soil
468 (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). Soil characteristics and processes may influence the extent to which
469 treated wastewater can influence microbial activities.

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470 The majority of the processes occurring in soils (80 – 90%) are facilitated by microbes and hence
471 an increase could lead to an improvement in soil fertility. The activities of soil microbiota are
472 considered as sensitive indicators in the determination of soil quality (Furtak & Gajda, 2017). In
473 agricultural production, these activities increase yield, promote seed germination and enhance
474 root growth. An example of such activities is the degradation of cellulose by β -glucosidase
475 enzymes (Adrover et al., 2012). Microbial activities lead to the release of growth regulators and
476 nutrients through the decomposition of organic matter thereby enhancing plant growth (Furtak &
477 Gajda, 2017).

478 **3.4.2 Microbial Population and Diversity**

479 Wastewater irrigation has the potential to affect the population and diversity of soil microbial
480 communities. Increase in population and different microbial species of wastewater irrigated soils
481 have been observed by several authors (Farhadkhani et al., 2018; Frenk et al., 2014; Hidri et al.,
482 2010; Wafula et al., 2015). The changes were species-specific, that is, some species were
483 favoured while others were not. By evaluating the microbial densities of long-term wastewater
484 irrigated soils, Hidri et al. (2010) revealed that the microbial abundances in the soil significantly
485 increased. They attributed the increase to the use of wastewater for the irrigation. The authors
486 argued that the rich carbon content of the wastewater may have caused the increase by promoting
487 the growth of microorganisms. As earlier on mentioned, changes in the microbial communities
488 were species-dependent. Frenk et al. (2014) recorded a reduction in the relative abundance of
489 *Actinobacteria* in a wastewater irrigated soil. However, the relative abundances of
490 *Gammaproteobacteria* increased by about 10%. Using a real-time polymerase chain reaction, the
491 total bacteria in both wastewater irrigated soils and freshwater irrigated soils were quantified, with
492 the former having a higher average bacteria abundance. In other wastewater irrigation studies,
493 increases in *Firmicutes*, *Betaproteobacteria*, *Acidobacteria*, and *Nitrospira* were observed. The

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494 irrigated soils had high bacterial community variability ratio (Ibekwe et al., 2018; Wafula et al.,
495 2015).

496 These increase could be beneficial for soil and plants considering the roles microbes play in the
497 plant-soil relationship. Microorganisms are involved in nutrients cycling and degradation
498 processes in soil. They convert organic nutrients into inorganic forms for easy absorption by
499 plants. Having a higher population and diversity of microorganisms may increase the rate of
500 cellulose degradation and nutrient cycling, making nutrients easily available for plants uptake.
501 Also, some of these microbes act as remediating agents against pesticides, heavy metals, and
502 antibiotics (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015; Hanjra et al., 2012) and hence help preserve soil integrity
503 and plant quality. The increase in microbial population and diversity may therefore promote plant
504 growth, ensure soil quality, and protect plants and soil against contaminants.

505 **4 Public Health Impacts**

506 Unlike potable water for domestic use, treated wastewater may contain pathogens, organic
507 pollutants or toxic substances (Yi et al., 2011) and heavy metals. These chemical constituents
508 and pathogens could pose health risk (Khalid et al., 2018) to farmers, farm workers and
509 consumers if not properly managed. Ingestion through food contamination and inhalation through
510 the respiratory system are the means by which the pathogens and contaminants can enter the
511 human body (Singh et al., 2012; Yi et al., 2011).

512 **4.1 Exposure to Pathogens**

513 Pathogens are disease causing microorganisms including bacteria, viruses, and protozoas.
514 Untreated wastewater contains different kinds of pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia*
515 *coli* (*E. coli*), intestinal nematodes and *Legionella* spp. These pathogens could still be present in
516 treated wastewater in high quantity particularly if disinfection or advanced filtration treatment such
517 as membranes are not part of the treatment train. High prevalence of enteric viruses has been

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518 observed in the effluent of a secondary treated wastewater with adenovirus being the most
519 prevalent (Schlindwein et al., 2010). Therefore, to protect public health, regulations and guidelines
520 are enacted by countries, regions and city authorities in the reuse of treated wastewater for
521 irrigation. Examples of such regulations and guidelines are Water Recycling Criteria (California-
522 USA), United States (US) Environmental Protection Agency Guidelines for Water Reuse, World
523 Health Organization Guidelines for Safe Use of Wastewater, Excreta and Greywater (US EPA,
524 2012), and the European Union (EU) Regulation No. 2020/741. However, the possibility of
525 exposure to pathogens still exists, especially for secondary treated wastewater and when the
526 guiding legislature is not adhere to properly. Wastewater reuse legislatures are country- and
527 region-specific and the risk of pathogen exposure could be relatively high for less stricter
528 regulations. Several water quality analyses of treated wastewater irrigation projects have revealed
529 the presence of pathogens or indicator bacteria in the irrigation water. Libutti et al. (2018) reported
530 in their study a significant amount of coliforms, fecal enterococci and *E. coli* in the secondary
531 treated wastewater effluent they used for the irrigation of tomatoes and broccoli. The *E. coli*
532 concentration was even above the limit set for reuse. Similar observation was made by Gatta et
533 al. (2016) who reported *E. coli* threshold far above the limit required by Italian law. Also in an
534 experimental trial in Lebanon, the irrigation water in most cases had higher fecal coliforms than
535 the World Health Organization proposed limit of 1000 CFU/100 mL (Mcheik et al., 2017). In all
536 these studies and many other cases, the pathogenic contamination of plant's edible parts were
537 not observed. Reason being that the type of irrigation system used help avoided direct contact
538 between plants and irrigation water. The assertions by the aforementioned authors suggest that
539 farmers and farm workers are at greater risk of exposure than consumers. Exposure to pathogens
540 may occur through direct contact with irrigation water or in the worst case food ingestion. The
541 latter has been the major concern of the public due to past experiences of food contamination.
542 Health wise such exposure may affect people negatively and could be fetal due to the harmful

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543 activities of these disease causing organisms. For example, *E. coli* has the potential to cause
544 diarrhea and extraintestinal diseases in humans and has been responsible for a number of
545 mortality issues globally (Croxen et al., 2013). Viruses present in the wastewater could cause
546 meningitis, encephalitis, hepatitis, gastrointestinal tract and respiratory tract infections in humans
547 (Okoh et al., 2010). Faecal coliforms on the other hand are not pathogenic, but are indicators of
548 the presence of disease causing organisms. Individuals exposed to wastewater containing high
549 coliforms are at greater health risk. The presence of indicator bacteria may indicate the presence
550 of dysentery, typhoid fever and bacterial gastroenteritis causing organisms (Oram, 2020).

551 Without proper and effective risk barrier systems, wastewater irrigation can cause public health
552 issues which may be difficult to manage. In line with this, the EU Regulation 2020/741 mandates
553 all forms of treated wastewater or reclaimed water use for irrigation to be disinfected prior to crop
554 application (European Commission, 2020). Great emphasis is placed on compliance of
555 microbiological parameters. Wastewater treatment plant operators, reclaimed water operators
556 and farmers who are the stakeholders in the demand and supply chain of treated wastewater
557 irrigation need to observe the risk barrier systems put in place to ensure the required
558 microbiological quality of irrigation water. Farmers should adopt barriers that prevent direct
559 contact of irrigation water with food. Sprinkler and furrow irrigation using treated wastewater
560 during fruiting and prior to harvesting should be discouraged since the possibility of water having
561 contact with fruits or edible parts is high. Pretreatment of vegetables after harvesting is necessary
562 to minimize exposure of the public or consumers to pathogens.

563 **4.2 Exposure to Heavy Metals**

564 Treated wastewater contains non-biodegradable and persistent pollutants such as heavy metals,
565 which can accumulate in the environment and enter the food chain (Cherfi et al., 2015). Despite
566 the fact that concentrations of heavy metals in irrigation wastewater are usually low (depending

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567 on the type of the wastewater and the level of its treatment), long-term irrigation poses a
568 perceptible risk for the environment and human health (Kim et al., 2015), as it can influence heavy
569 metals uptake by plants. Heavy metals may influence plant metabolism, photosynthesis and
570 stomatal opening, which are related to plant growth (Parveen et al., 2015) and can also affect
571 microbial communities or cause phytotoxicity (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). Heavy metals
572 availability and mobility depend on various factors such as their form, cations exchange capacity
573 (Rezapour et al., 2019), temperature, humidity, organic matter, pH, nutrients content (Kim et al.,
574 2015), soil conditions, and type of plant (Dickin et al., 2016). Results from Qureshi et al. (2016)
575 show the differences in heavy metals uptake, which are distinctly higher in leafy vegetables than
576 in root and food crops. Heavy metals tend to accumulate mostly in the surface soil due to their
577 low solubility and limited plant uptake (Kim et al., 2015), but after longer periods of irrigation with
578 wastewater, heavy metals can also affect groundwater (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015).
579 Accumulation of heavy metals in plants is not uniform – generally, they are more concentrated in
580 the roots than in the leaves or the edible parts of the plant (Parveen et al., 2015).

581 Effects of heavy metals on human health are well-known, for instance, some heavy metals can
582 cause cancer, while others are harmful to nervous, skeletal, circulatory, enzymatic, endocrine, or
583 immune systems, and vital organs (Cherfi et al., 2015). There may be also a risk of synergistic
584 effect with other contaminants, such as antibiotics (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015). Series of studies
585 (Nikaido et al., 2010; Parveen et al., 2015; Rezapour et al., 2019) claim that irrigation with
586 wastewater cause a significant build-up of heavy metals concentrations in plants in comparison
587 to potable water. Although Rezapour et al. (2019) noted cadmium and copper concentrations
588 above the tolerable limits, most of the studies (Nikaido et al., 2010; Parveen et al., 2015; Qureshi
589 et al., 2016) assessed the concentrations of heavy metals in the plants as safe for human
590 consumption according to contemporary limits.

591 **5 Economic Impacts**

592 To better understand and properly assess the trade-offs of treated wastewater reuse for irrigation,
593 it is important to consider the economic cost and benefits of such a scheme (Garcia & Pargament,
594 2015). Detailed economic and technical case study analyses to establish the feasibility of a reuse
595 project has been done by Giannoccaro et al. (2019) and Verlicchi et al. (2012).

596 **5.1 Farm Expenditure and Income**

597 In the region of Tiznit (Morocco), reuse of treated wastewater for crop irrigation significantly
598 improved the income and standard of living of farmers. The farmers made savings on chemical
599 fertilizers while at the same time experience increased crop yield due to the fertilizing effect of the
600 treated wastewater (Malki et al., 2017). Macronutrients (N, P, K) together with micronutrients
601 supplied to crops by wastewater help farmers make savings on fertilizer purchase by reducing
602 fertilizer usage. For instance, wastewater irrigation can reduce chemical fertilizer usage by 45%
603 and 94% in wheat and alfalfa cultivation respectively (Balkhair et al., 2013). Vergine et al. (2017a)
604 evaluated and estimated the potential savings of wastewater irrigation for tomato cultivation and
605 found savings potential of €280/ha. In another economic evaluation, Reznik et al. (2017)
606 estimated that treated wastewater irrigation could increase Israel's present welfare by US \$3.3
607 billion. Their study made use of Israel's version of the Multi-Year Water Allocation System
608 (MYWAS) mathematical programming model, and on the condition that the treated wastewater
609 will not be further desalinated. Even though these economic benefit evaluations are localized,
610 their replications in other places of similar characteristics may not deviate widely in regards to the
611 expected outcomes. Similar assertion with respect to replication is also shared by (Arborea et al.,
612 2017). In addition to direct and indirect income to farmers (sales from higher yield and fertilizer
613 savings), wastewater irrigation offers non-market benefits to society. That is the monetary value
614 for the contribution to the preservation of water resources. Using wastewater to irrigate crops
615 reduce water stress on existing freshwater resources and prevents the discharge of effluents into

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616 water resources. However, in many instances these contributions are not monetized and the non-
617 market value neglected. The non-market value could be as high as €0.31 per cubic meter of water
618 and even could exceed the cost of polishing the treated wastewater for reuse (Alcon et al., 2010).
619 The economic benefits are enormous and are both monetary and non-monetary but very often
620 the latter is neglected.

5.2 Increased Crop Production

621 Water is very essential for crop production. It is considered as one of the major limiting factors in
622 the productivity of crops (Villalobos et al., 2016). Crop production requires continuous supply of
623 water to meet crop water requirement and avoid water stress. Because water stress adversely
624 affects the morphological and physiological processes of crops and leads to lower harvestable
625 yield (Sadras et al., 2016). In the Po Valley of Italy, surface water withdrawal controls caused by
626 frequent drought led to reduction in crop yield and income loss of about 20% - 30% (Verlicchi et
627 al., 2012). Wastewater irrigation do not only supply nutrients to boost crop production but also
628 makes water available for farmers to boost their yield. Since wastewater is climate independent
629 (unlike rainfall), farmers could have continuous access to water for crop irrigation even during
630 drought period (Verlicchi et al., 2012). This affords farmers the opportunity to maintain optimal
631 soil moisture of their farms/fields, and achieve stable and higher crop yields (Ouda et al., 2016)
632 regardless of the season. Usually, wastewater reuse schemes produce enough water to meet the
633 irrigation demands and therefore, continuous availability of water can be guaranteed.

5.3 Direct Financial Benefits to WWTPs

634 WWTPs could benefit financially from wastewater irrigation through the reduction of energy
635 consumption. In the case where WWTPs must pump effluent from treatment site to receiving
636 water body, a considerable amount of money could be saved on pumping. This was the case at
637 the Ferrara WWTP in Italy. A technical and economic analyses of a reuse project revealed that
638
639

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640 the plant could lower its pumping cost by €200,000.00 annually (Verlicchi et al., 2012). The
641 reduction was due to a change in conveyance distance of treated wastewater from 5 km to 2 km
642 as a result of the reuse project. Another factor that could contribute to reduction in pumping cost
643 is the reduction in the volume of effluent to be pumped. Diverting part of the WWTP outflow for
644 irrigation may lower the amount of effluent to be discharged and subsequently the energy
645 required. For instance, Giannoccaro et al. (2019) estimated that about 97 million m³/year of
646 treated wastewater could be technically recovered in Puglia (Italy) for irrigation. Clearly, this
647 reduction would lead to lower pumping cost with regards to direct discharge. Even though the
648 conveyance of such a recoverable volume will incur a cost, the economic and environmental
649 benefits arising from the irrigation exercise may totally or partially offset the incurred cost.

650 Financial benefits could also be realized from the reduction in fees paid to regulators by WWTP
651 operators; that is the polluter pay principle, which in some countries mandate WWTP to pay a
652 certain fee for discharge into water resources. Usually, the fee is volume or loading rate
653 dependent, and therefore a reduction in the volume of effluent discharged, could translates into
654 financial savings.

655 Economic benefits arising from the direct usage of wastewater for augmenting river flow, and
656 creation of new recreational areas and wetlands (Alcon et al., 2012; Verlicchi et al., 2012) are
657 beyond the scope of this paper and therefore not discussed.

658 **5.4 Extra Investment Cost**

659 Wastewater irrigation incurs additional cost to both wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) operators
660 and farmers. Additional investment cost arising from polishing of effluent to meet reuse
661 requirements, transportation and storage costs. Transportation cost incorporates the cost of
662 reservoir, piping and pumping needed to transport the treated wastewater to the end-users (Ruiz-
663 Rosa et al., 2016). In instances where farmers do not have direct access to the treated wastewater

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664 at the treatment facility, transportation and storage infrastructures are required. Unfortunately,
665 existing potable water distribution lines cannot be used to transport the wastewater to the farmers
666 hence calling for the construction of new distribution lines. An alternative to the distribution lines
667 is the use of tanker trucks which will also require storage tanks at farms. The provision of these
668 capital intensive infrastructures can burden the end-users (farmers) and WWTP operators
669 financially, if no proper financial support exists. Wastewater intended for agricultural irrigation
670 should satisfy certain quality standards due to safety and public health concerns. However, many
671 biological conventional treated wastewater fall short of these standards and therefore require
672 further polishing. The cost of this further treatment could be between €0.13 and €0.23 per cubic
673 meter of water as was the case of Murcia (Spain) (Alcon et al., 2010). Without proper incentives
674 and market value, operators will struggle to cover this additional cost and farmers on the other
675 hand have to deal with higher cost of water for irrigation, which could adversely affect their income.

6 Trace Organic Compounds, Microplastics, and Antibiotic Resistant Genes and Bacteria

677 These are class of compounds or species with known or perceived risk to humans and the
678 ecosystem. Trace organic compounds or contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) incorporates
679 a wide range of compounds including pharmaceuticals and their transformation products or
680 metabolites, personal care products, endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs), etc (Kassinis et
681 al., 2011). A number of studies globally, have detected the presence of these compounds in
682 wastewater effluents. In Europe, drugs such as ibuprofen, diclofenac, ketoprofen and naproxen
683 have been detected in effluents (Li et al., 2010). Diaz-Sosa et al. (2020) identified 37 CECs in the
684 secondary effluent of the Prague wastewater treatment plant in Czech Republic. Another study in
685 Canada, found CECs (triclosan, caffeine, testosterone) in the treated effluent of a wastewater
686 treatment plant (WWTP) (Basiuk et al., 2017). Commercial and household pharmaceuticals and
687 personal care products (PPCPs) are some of the sources of these substances in wastewater
688 (Tong et al., 2011; Diaz-Sosa et al., 2020). Human excretion and disposal of unwanted drugs into

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689 sewage are some of the routes by which the CECs enters the wastewater stream (Tong et al.,
690 2011).

691 The detection of trace organic compounds in treated wastewater could cast doubts on the safety
692 of wastewater irrigation because of the known or perceived adverse effects of some of the
693 compounds (eg. EDCs). EDCs may change the reproduction, development, neural and immune
694 functions of organisms by mimicking endogenous hormones (Basiuk et al., 2017; NIH, HHS
695 2010). Knowledge on CECs with regards to wastewater irrigation is relatively limited and at early
696 stages. Relatively few studies have been done on the bioaccessibility, bioaccumulation and
697 bioavailability of these trace compounds with respect to treated wastewater irrigation. Kassinos
698 et al. (2011) highlights some of the findings from these studies as: (i) Soils irrigated with
699 wastewater had higher CECs, indicating possible accumulation of CECs in soil from wastewater.
700 (ii) Uptake of CECs by plants, and in some cases resulted in toxicity, suggesting possible
701 bioaccumulation. More studies are needed to better understand the fate of these organics in
702 relation to plant uptake, accumulation, and transfer within the food chain under wastewater
703 irrigation.

704 Like PPCPs and EDCs, microplastics (MPs) are another group of emerging contaminants that
705 can be found in treated wastewater (Blair et al., 2017). They are pieces of plastics with less than
706 5 mm diameter and originate from a wide range of sources such as textiles and packaging (Kay
707 et al., 2018). One of the sources and routes by which MPs are released into the environment is
708 through discharge of effluent from WWTPs (Blair et al., 2017; Roex et al., 2017; Sol et al., 2020).
709 Studies on these contaminants have mainly focused on aquatic ecosystem particularly, the
710 marine ecosystem (Horton et al., 2017; Kay et al., 2018; Leslie et al., 2013; Westphalen &
711 Abdelrasoul, 2018), their presence in wastewater, and treatment (Conley et al., 2019; Kay et al.,
712 2018; Leslie et al., 2013; Sol et al., 2020); with very limited studies on soil (He et al., 2018; Hurley

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713 & Nizzetto, 2018). A study conducted in England by Kay et al. (2018) found higher levels of MPs
714 in the downstream of the receiving waters of six WWTPs. The authors concluded that effluent
715 discharges from the WWTPs were the main cause of the high MPs levels. Bioaccumulation of
716 MPs (mainly fibers) were observed in some marine biota (oysters, periwinkle, mussel) in another
717 study conducted in the Netherlands (Leslie et al., 2013). Ingestion of these substances may block
718 digestive tracts, choke, damage organs and cause fatality in organisms (Blair et al., 2017).

719 Direct studies of MPs involving wastewater irrigation are non-existing or rare to the best of our
720 knowledge. Notwithstanding, knowledge of MPs regarding accessibility, availability and
721 accumulation in aquatic and soil ecosystems could provide clues to the risks that might arise from
722 wastewater irrigation. Irrigating plants with wastewater may not pose a direct risk to plants since
723 direct uptake of MPs by plants is unlikely (Hurley & Nizzetto, 2018). However, wastewater
724 irrigation can lead to deposition of MPs into agriculture soils and negatively impact the soil's
725 integrity and fauna. MPs could also introduce other contaminants (persistent organic pollutants
726 (POPs), metals, other CECs) into soil because of their hydrophobic surface which enables them
727 to adsorb other contaminants (Blair et al., 2017; He et al., 2018; Horton et al., 2017). This
728 degrades the quality of the soil and could induce toxicity in plants through the uptake of adsorbed
729 contaminants (heavy metals, POPs, CECs). These contaminants pose health risk to both humans
730 and animals through the food chain. In addition, MPs together with their adsorbed contaminants
731 could be leached out of the soil into groundwater, representing a potential exposure pathway to
732 humans (He et al., 2018; Hurley & Nizzetto, 2018). These risks call for removal of these
733 contaminants in effluent prior to land application. Research on risk assessments regarding
734 wastewater irrigation and microplastics is strongly recommended to better understand the impacts
735 of these substances in wastewater irrigation.

736 **7 Way-forward**

737 Many systems and concepts of our world are not without benefits and drawbacks. The concept
738 and practice of treated wastewater for crop irrigation are not an exception as have been
739 demonstrated in this paper. This section outlines and discusses interventions that could be
740 adopted to maximize the benefits of treated wastewater irrigation and to reduce the negative
741 impacts associated with the practice. Further contribution to existing knowledge is also
742 highlighted.

743 **7.1 Water Recovery**

744 The priority of wastewater irrigation should be water recovery and not nutrient supply. A lot of the
745 adverse environmental impacts mitigating against the widespread application of this reuse arise
746 from the nutrients and salts contents of the wastewater. While these nutrients can be beneficial
747 to plants, they are also capable of causing damage to soil, water resources and crop production.
748 Groundwater pollution, soil salinization and plant toxicity could all be linked to nutrients and salts
749 content of the treated wastewater. Recovering water to support agriculture and address water
750 scarcity should be the primary focus of any reuse scheme, especially in regions of water shortages
751 (Mediterranean, semi-arid and arid regions). The growing water demand coupled with increasing
752 water deficit are drivers promoting marginal quality water usage in agriculture. Focusing on water
753 recovery will place demand on high marginal water quality and improved treatment options. From
754 the review, most of the observed negative environmental impacts were associated with secondary
755 treated wastewater. The irrigation water was relatively high in nutrients, salts or ions and the water
756 was considered appropriate in many cases partly because of the fertilization effect. The treatment
757 systems were basically conventional biological treatment and did not incorporate advanced
758 treatment. It is evident that one of the motivational drivers for using treated wastewater to irrigates
759 crops is the fertilization effect, however, it has also raised serious environmental concerns if not

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760 effectively managed. Critics often cite groundwater pollution caused by leaching of nutrients
761 (nitrates, salts) and soil salinization.

762 Another drawback that could be addressed by the concept of prioritizing water recovery is the risk
763 to public health. That is the health impact arising from exposure to pathogens and heavy metals.

764 It has been one of the strongest oppositions to the widespread implementation of wastewater
765 reuse in agriculture. Even-though several studies have suggested less health risk in the usage of
766 secondary treated wastewater, public perceptions in this regard often do not favour its adoption.

767 For majority of the public, the fact that the wastewater could contain an appreciable amount of
768 pathogens and heavy metals, implies that it is not safe for irrigation. Prioritizing water recovery in
769 reuse schemes calls for inclusion of advanced treatment processes such as membrane processes
770 (microfiltration, ultrafiltration and nanofiltration) and ultraviolet (UV) disinfection to produce high

771 quality irrigation water in terms of microbial load and heavy metals content. These technologies
772 are already in the market, and some countries like Spain and Italy have started incorporating
773 microfiltration and ultrafiltration into their agricultural wastewater reuse schemes. Nanofiltration
774 treatment process in agricultural irrigation reuse scheme is almost non-existing to the best of our
775 knowledge. Incorporating these advanced processes, especially nanofiltration, will not only

776 minimize the environmental impact issues arising from high nutrients and salts content, but also
777 the public health concerns arising from pathogens and heavy metals. The produced irrigation
778 water will be high in quality and could support plant growth without any higher risk to health, soil,
779 water resources and plants. Enhancing the quality of treated wastewater through disinfection must

780 be an integral part of every wastewater irrigation scheme. Disinfection improves the quality of
781 water by destroying pathogenic organisms that might pose threat to public health. It ensures that
782 farmers, farm workers and the public are protected from exposure to pathogens. The use of UV

783 disinfection is recommended as a preferred choice to other forms of disinfection. UV is very
784 effective in destroying most pathogenic microorganisms and does not leave by-products or

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785 residues in the treated water. A combination of UV disinfection and membrane technology could
786 produce treated wastewater of high quality equivalent to freshwater. Such high quality water will
787 not only eliminate or reduce the environmental and health risks but also could increase the
788 confidence of the public in wastewater irrigation and therefore promote its acceptance globally.

789 A major concern to the incorporation of these treatment options in agricultural irrigation is the
790 relatively high cost of the system. But such cost is justifiable considering the market and non-
791 market value of the recovered water as well as the benefit of preserving the quality of agriculture
792 soils (non-renewable resource). Already, some studies have even confirmed the economic
793 viability of incorporating such advance treatment systems in wastewater irrigation.

794 **7.2 Localization and Piloting**

795 The adoption of treated wastewater for agricultural irrigation should be localized and piloted. The
796 type and extent of impact of wastewater on plants, soil and water resources is not independent of
797 soil characteristics, plant physiology and morphology, climate and other factors. Soil structure and
798 texture, pH, and soil hydraulic properties all influence greatly the environmental impacts of
799 wastewater irrigation. Different soils react differently to wastewater and therefore localizing
800 wastewater reuse could maximize the benefits and minimize the negative impacts. For instance,
801 the response of sandy soil to treated wastewater high in salinity or nutrients would be different
802 from that of loamy soil or clayey soil. Such responses are also true for plants; while some plants
803 have high tolerance level for salts and nutrients, others do not. In the work of Paudel et al. (2016),
804 the application of treated wastewater for plant irrigation influenced the specific root area, tissue
805 density and cortex area of plants cultivated in clay soil but no influence was observed for the
806 sandy-loam counterpart. Also the increase in salt uptake by plants cultivated in clay soil was
807 higher than that of sandy-loam. Better understanding and knowledge of the aforementioned
808 issues can be obtained through the implementation of pilot projects which will help adopt location-

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809 specific reuse scheme. Pilot project could provide useful information on potential challenges,
810 environmental and health impacts as well as economic feasibility of wastewater irrigation. Such
811 knowledge can help minimize issues like leaching of nutrients into groundwater, salinization of
812 soil, clogging of soil pores, over application of fertilizers, plant toxicity and exposure to pathogens
813 and heavy metals that may be encountered in a larger reuse scheme. Piloting should focus on:
814 (i) setting reuse guidelines and regulations that are localized or country specific and (ii)
815 implementation of risk prevention barriers for the protection of public health and environmental
816 safety.

817 The high cost of transporting treated wastewater to agricultural end-users is a major disincentive
818 to wastewater irrigation. However, this cost can be avoided or reduced significantly by siting
819 wastewater treatment plants in close proximity to arable lands, if local conditions permit. Because
820 the use of treated wastewater for irrigation was not included in mainstream planning in many
821 countries, treatment plants turn to be further away from agricultural lands. Conveying treated
822 wastewater over such long distances is expensive. Siting future wastewater treatment plants
823 closer to arable lands could reduce considerably both the investment and operational (pumping)
824 costs of transporting the water to farmers. In principle shorter pipe length, less time and less
825 energy would be required.

826 **8 Conclusion**

827 The application of treated wastewater in agricultural irrigation presents environmental, health and
828 economic challenges as well as benefits. While some benefits and drawbacks can easily be
829 characterized, others are complicated and localized. Risk of exposure to pathogens and heavy
830 metals, and salinization of soil are easily characterized as drawbacks. Nutrients supply, water
831 resources protection and savings, and farm profitability are the identified pros. Wastewater
832 irrigation has increased over the years due to these benefits especially in regions of water scarcity

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833 but also the associated challenges have prevented the widespread use globally particularly in
834 areas of no or low water deficit. The type and severity of impact of wastewater irrigation on soil,
835 water resources and public health are not only dependent on the quality of the wastewater but
836 also on soil characteristics, plant physiology and morphology, climate, type of irrigation and
837 agricultural management practices. Agricultural irrigation using treated wastewater could promote
838 both agriculture and water sustainabilities but the primary focus of such a practice should be water
839 recovery and its adoption localized. The feasibility of reuse scheme is dependent on a number of
840 factors including technical, social and economic issues. The evaluation of these issues needs
841 adequate and consolidated tools as well as field experience. We conclude that treated wastewater
842 certainly has great prospect of being a viable alternate water source for irrigation but risk
843 prevention barriers should be adopted to mitigate the negative impacts.

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